

Addition of Diazomethane on Strongly Electrophillic Olefins

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The 1-3 dipolar cycloaddition reactions of diazomethane have been studied with dipolarophiles with one potential site of attack. In order to see the mechanism of these dipolar additions more closely it was desirable to use dipolarophiles having multicentres where the dipoles could attack. Only recently such studies have been carried on where dipolarophiles contained C = C and C = N bond in conjugation and the dipoles, include nitrile oxide, nitrile imines and diazomethane¹⁻³. Here dipoles attacked more polar carbon-nitrogen bond rather than carbon-carbon bond. This report describes reaction of diazomethane with substituted butadienes.

The cinnamylidene ethylcyanoacetate¹ obtained from cinnamaldehyde and ethyl cyanoacetate through Knoevengel condensation was allowed to react with ethereal solution of diazomethane (excess) at 0°, and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for two days at R.T. The solvent was then removed under vacuum at room temperature and the residue thus obtained on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether mixture gave light yellow crystalline compound, m.p. 98-99° in 80% yield. The elemental analysis, i.r., n.m.r., and the mass spectrum supported structure (II) for this compound.

The mass spectrum showed M⁺ at m/e 241 which corresponds to M.F. C₁₅H₁₅NO₂. (Calcd. C, 74.69; H, 6.23; N, 5.81; Found: C, 74.58; H, 6.8; N, 5.60).

In n.m.r. spectrum 60 MHz in CDCl₃ of (I) did not show any absorption in olefinic region as the three olefinic protons were merged with aromatic protons (8H multiplet centred at 2.5τ). The n.m.r. spectrum of (II) 60 MHz in CDCl₃ showed the presence of two olefinic protons in the region 3-4τ, one proton at 3-1τ (1H, doublet) and second proton at 3.6τ (1H, multiplet). This change can only be interpreted if structure (II) is assigned to the new

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compound where extended conjugation upto nitrile and ester groups has been blocked. In i.r. spectrum of (I) $\text{CH} = \text{CH}$ *trans* is indicated at 980 cm^{-1} , $\text{C} = \text{O}$ (conjugated) at 1720 cm^{-1} and $\text{C} = \text{N}$ at 2250 cm^{-1} (s). The i.r. spectrum of (II) shows three bands at 970 cm^{-1} , 1740 cm^{-1} , and 2250 cm^{-1} (w). This change of intensity of $\text{C} = \text{N}$ absorption is due to the change of Sp^2 to Sp^3 hybridization of the carbon to which cyanide group is attached⁴. In mass spectrum along with the parent peak (M^+) at m/e 241, the other prominent peaks were at m/e 213 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_2\text{H}_4$), m/e 212 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), m/e 196 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O}$), m/e 168 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$), m/e 153, m/e 141, m/e 103, m/e 91 and m/e 77.

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